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IMPROVING THE GRAMMAR SKILLS OF LANGUAGE LEARNERS USING ICT TECHNOLOGIES

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***Annotation.** A modern school is unthinkable without the use of ICT. The opportunities now available to teachers not only diversify the learning process but also make it more effective and efficient. Organizing in-class and extracurricular activities using ICT proves much more engaging not only for students but also for the teacher. Photographs and texts, the introduction of sound and animation, and various effects—all of this aids teachers in teaching Russian language and literature, enabling them to organize student activities so that they master the curriculum at a higher level.*

***Key words:** Modern school, use of ICT, educational process, effective and efficient, organization of classroom and extracurricular activities using ICT.*

Today, it is undeniable that teaching foreign language grammar, more than any other activity, requires the use of the broadest range of teaching methods, teaching aids, and multimedia programs, organized into a unified system to support the learning process. In other words, to improve the quality of instruction in such a complex aspect of the English language as grammar, it is essential to implement modern trends in the computerization of the learning process as a highly effective way to enhance knowledge and motivation.

An integral part of the informatization of education is the use of information and communication technologies (ICT). Their use is guided by the Federal State

Educational Standard, which emphasizes the importance of developing students' ICT competencies to enhance the effectiveness of developing independent knowledge acquisition skills.

According to the new National Curriculum (Education Standard) of Uzbekistan, the term ICT refers to information processes and methods of working with information, carried out using computing technology and telecommunications [www.standartgost.ru]. ICT is a broad, general concept that includes technologies such as computer, multimedia, and interactive technologies.

The main advantages of using ICT include the intensification and individualization of learning, which yield positive results by creating conditions for each student's success, evoking positive emotions in learners, and thus contributing to increased interest in the subject and the productivity of self-study. New information technologies ensure high-quality presentation of material through the use of various communication channels and help fill the gap in educational resources. Undoubted advantages of using ICT also include accelerated dissemination and access to pedagogical achievements, reduced time for obtaining and assimilating information without loss of quality, and increased flexibility in the learning process. Furthermore, the use of computers and digital educational resources in foreign language teaching helps students overcome the psychological barrier to using a foreign language as a means of communication, developing their communicative, cognitive, and creative abilities, as well as their information literacy [Grigoriev 2008: 34].

The most common ICT elements are:

- Electronic encyclopedias and reference books,
- Online educational resources,
- Simulators and testing programs,
- DVDs and CDs with pictures and illustrations,
- Electronic textbooks and interactive materials displayed using a computer and multimedia projector,
- Distance learning competitions and distance learning.

The primary means of implementing ICT in a modern school classroom are a computer, a multimedia projector, and a screen.

ICT can be used in a grammar lesson on any topic and at any stage of the grammar process. With proper placement, appropriate color schemes, the use of diagrams and tables, and voice-over, students will understand the rules more easily and quickly. Moreover, by using new information technologies, it is possible to carry out an interesting form of monitoring the level of development of grammatical skills based on testing programs and a system for detecting grammatical errors at the morphological and syntactic levels.

In my teaching practice, I use multimedia presentations (MPPs) created in Microsoft PowerPoint when introducing grammar concepts. When studying grammar, it's important to highlight the most complex and important information using animation. Animating objects allows students to further focus their attention on important components. Presentations that include exercises for initial reinforcement after the explanation or presentation of the material have proven to be the most productive. Students complete these exercises directly on the screen, either individually or face-to-face. The ability to show the correct answer allows for quick and effective peer or self-testing.

In addition to MMPs, online resources can be used for initial reinforcement:

<http://www.e-grammar.org>

<http://study-english.info/grammar.php>

<http://englisch-infoblog.ru>

<http://www.study.ru> and others.

During the grammar skill development stage, an interactive whiteboard offers a wide range of opportunities. Its sensitive surface allows you to control educational software, add information and questions to text or images on the screen, and select and move objects on the board or group them by specific characteristics. Examples of interactive whiteboard exercises:

- Circle / Underline the correct answer;

- Tick / Cross out;
- Fill in the gaps in these sentences;
- Complete the sentences with...;
- Correct the following words / sentences;
- Put... in the correct order;
- Match the phrase and its translation;
- Write the words in the chart.

I believe it is advisable to monitor the assimilation of the material covered using such an effective tool as computer testing, performed in Microsoft Excel or the My Test program. But to save time, you can use the following tests:

<http://www.englishteststore.net>

<http://nsportal.ru>

<http://onlinetestpad.com>

<http://www.learnenglish-online.com>

<http://engtime.ru> and others.

Thus, the new capabilities of ICT tools highlight the importance of their use at every stage of working with grammar material, as they enable students to achieve a sufficiently high level of grammatical skills. Analyzing the experience of using ICT, we can confidently say that modern information technology tools allow us to expand and expand the scope of grammar teaching; enrich English language learning methods with new forms and examples, making them more effective.

However, the use of ICT can also lead to a number of negative consequences, including an unacceptable increase in the volume of educational information, visual fatigue, and deterioration of the nervous system. A rational solution to the negative impact of new information technologies on educational participants is to design lessons that take sanitary requirements into account, organize activities wisely, follow the recommendations of psychologists and doctors, constantly monitor the reactions of educational participants, and promptly implement corrections.

One of the main advantages of using ICT in foreign language learning is access to an unlimited amount of materials. Previously, students were limited to textbooks, teachers, and classroom lessons, but today they can use a variety of online resources, such as video lectures, audio podcasts, e-books and articles, as well as language forums. This allows learners to develop all aspects of language proficiency: listening, reading, speaking, and writing.

Furthermore, ICT facilitates the individualization of the learning process. Many digital platforms offer adaptive programs that take into account the student's level of preparation, pace, and needs. For example, apps like Duolingo and Babbel offer tasks of varying difficulty depending on their language proficiency. This allows students to learn at their own pace, reviewing materials as needed.

Multimedia technologies also have a significant impact on student motivation. Interactive tasks, the ability to communicate with native speakers via video conferencing or chat, and participation in virtual language clubs make the learning process more engaging and dynamic.

Interactive platforms and apps are central to modern language learning. Resources like Duolingo, Memrise, Quizlet, and LinguaLeo offer learners the opportunity to learn languages using game elements, significantly increasing motivation. Gamification is the use of game mechanics for educational purposes. For example, on Duolingo, students earn points for completing assignments correctly, encouraging them to complete more lessons and improve their skills.

Quizlet, meanwhile, allows learners to create their own sets of flashcards to memorize new vocabulary and grammar structures. These sets can be used for both independent and group work, making the learning process more flexible and interactive. These platforms also allow learners to develop listening and speaking skills through audio recordings and dialogue simulations. Furthermore, modern platforms provide instant feedback, helping learners correct errors in real time and improve their results.

Video Conferencing and Virtual Classrooms. Video conferencing became especially popular during the COVID-19 pandemic, when educational institutions were forced to switch to distance learning. Using platforms such as Zoom, Microsoft Teams, and Google Meet, teachers were able to continue teaching by using videoconferencing for lessons. This allowed students to engage in live communication, practice speaking skills, and even practice the language with native speakers. Video conferencing not only facilitates access to learning for students in remote areas but also allows them to participate in international language clubs and projects. Furthermore, it creates an environment for collaborative work on assignments, which improves communication skills and helps overcome language barriers.

One of the most important aspects of using video conferencing is the ability to instantly correct errors and receive feedback from the teacher. However, it is worth noting that this format requires certain technical skills and a stable internet connection, which may be challenging in some regions.

Using ICT for Assessment. ICTs offer numerous opportunities for assessing knowledge and monitoring student progress. Online tests, assignments, and automated assessment systems (such as those on platforms like Kahoot and Socrative) allow teachers to assess students' knowledge in real time. This simplifies the testing and performance analysis process, making it possible to track each student's progress.

Platforms such as Google Classroom and Moodle also allow teachers to create online courses, post assignments, and have students submit their work electronically. This facilitates the organization of the learning process and makes it more transparent.

A modern school is unthinkable without the use of ICT. The opportunities now available to teachers not only diversify the learning process but also make it more effective and efficient. Organizing in-class and extracurricular activities using ICT proves much more engaging not only for students but also for the teacher. Photographs and texts, the introduction of sound and animation, and various effects all assist teachers in teaching Russian language and literature, enabling them to organize students' activities so that they master the curriculum at a higher level.

For example, using electronic textbooks in Russian language and literature lessons allows teachers to optimize the learning process and expand the amount of information students can receive per lesson. The electronic Russian language textbook "Cyril and Methodius: Russian Language for Grades 5-11" is such a textbook. The vibrant tables and graphs, unique exercises, and exercise machines are very engaging for children.

PowerPoint presentation programs are also actively used at all stages of Russian language and literature lessons. Pre-prepared presentations not only help organize an engaging lesson or extracurricular activity, but also save the teacher time.

Many useful programs, ready-made tests, exercises, and lesson materials can be found on the website www.school-collection.ru.

The interactive whiteboard offers a wealth of possibilities. It is especially effective in Russian language lessons during the explanation or reinforcement of the material in the sections "Spelling" and "Punctuation."

Therefore, in and outside of the classroom, using ICT capabilities, teachers can organize the learning process in a way that enriches it with new content, making it productive and engaging. Integrating information and communication technologies into the teaching of Russian language and literature is not only possible but also necessary today, but it must be systematic. Every stage of a lesson or activity must be carefully planned by the teacher before they even enter the classroom. Literature lessons focus on creativity, text comprehension, and word processing. Here, of course, ICT is always helpful. Video clips about authors' biographies, audio recordings of works, and film screenings based on works of fiction...However, it is important to recognize that automated assessment systems have their limitations, as they cannot always account for subjective aspects of language proficiency, such as intonation, pronunciation, and creative use of language. Therefore, it is important for teachers to combine the use of ICTs with traditional assessment methods to gain a comprehensive understanding of student skills.

Problems and Challenges in Using ICT in Teaching

Despite its many advantages, using ICT in foreign language teaching poses a number of challenges. One of these is its technical complexity. Not all students have access to high-speed internet or the necessary devices, creating an uneven learning environment. The problem of digital inequality is particularly acute in regions with low levels of technological development.

ICT can be used to stimulate students' cognitive interest. Cognitive interest is the primary intrinsic motivation for learning, so developing an interest in Russian language and literature is particularly important for teachers. To achieve this, it is essential to use information and communication technologies in the classroom, as the vast potential of ICT (systematization, richness, engaging content, and the portability of information) undoubtedly increases students' interest in the lesson and the subject, thereby enhancing and guaranteeing improved learning. The Education Modernization Strategy emphasizes the need to change teaching methods and technologies at all levels, increasing the emphasis on those that develop practical skills in information analysis and self-study, encourage independent work, and foster the experience of responsible choice and action.

Of course, the above does not mean that lessons must now be conducted using ICT and that all presentation of educational material must be delegated to the computer. Teachers can and should alternate between various teaching methods. For example, the teacher may explain part of a lesson themselves, while others may use an electronic assistant. Consequently, when studying a topic, computer support should not be overused, nor should any other single method of work. The following tasks face the informatization of education: - improving the quality of student training through the use of modern information technologies in the educational process; - applying active teaching methods, enhancing the creative and intellectual components of learning activities; - integrating various types of educational activities (academic, research, etc.);

– adaptation of information technologies for teaching to the individual characteristics of the student; – development of new information technologies for

teaching that promote the activation of the student's cognitive activity and increase the motivation to master the means and methods of informatics for effective application in professional activity; – ensuring continuity and succession in teaching; – development of information technologies for distance learning; – improvement of software and methodological support of the educational process. The content of the teacher's activity is changing; the teacher ceases to be simply a “reproducer” of knowledge, becoming a developer of new teaching technology, which, on the one hand, increases his creative activity, and on the other, requires a high level of technological and methodological training. A new area of the teacher's activity has appeared – the development of information technologies for teaching and software and methodological educational complexes.

There is also the danger of information overload. Too many digital tools and resources can confuse students and lead to a decrease in their concentration and motivation. Therefore, it is important to plan the learning process carefully and avoid overloading it with unnecessary elements.

Conclusion. Information and communication technologies (ICTs) offer new opportunities for foreign language learning. They facilitate individualized learning, increase student motivation, and make the learning process more interactive and accessible. However, when using them, it is important to consider technical and psychological aspects to avoid overload and resource access issues.

The role of ICTs in education will only grow in the future, requiring teachers and students to be prepared to continuously master new tools and technologies.

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